

Supplementary Information

Synthesis and fluorescent properties of some benzothiazole derivatives synthesized *via* Suzuki cross coupling reaction

Nguyen Hien^a, Nguyen Van Dat^a, Nguyen Duc Du^a, Nguyen Thi Ngoc Mai^b, Nguyen Thi Thu Hien^c & Duong

Quoc Hoan^{*a}

^a Department of Chemistry, Hanoi National University of Education, Hanoi, 100000 Vietnam

^b Department of Science, Hong Duc University, Thanh Hoa, 440000 Vietnam

^c Department of Geography, Hanoi National University of Education, Hanoi, 100000 Vietnam

E-mail: hoandq@hnue.edu.vn

Received 23 September 2023; accepted (revised) 24 November 2023

Contents

1. ¹H NMR spectra of compounds	2
2. ¹³C NMR spectra of compounds	7
3. MS spectra of compounds	12

1. ¹H NMR spectra of compounds

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2c

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2d

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2g

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2h

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2i

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2j

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2k

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2l

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2n

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2n

2. ^{13}C NMR spectra of compounds

^{13}C NMR spectra of compound 2c

^{13}C NMR spectra of compound 2d

¹³C NMR spectra of compound 2g

¹³C NMR spectra of compound 2h

¹³C NMR spectra of compound 2k

¹³C NMR spectra of compound 2l

^{13}C NMR spectra of compound 2n

^{13}C NMR spectra of compound 2o

3. MS spectra of compounds

MS spectra of compound 2c

MS spectra of compound 2d

MS spectra of compound 2f

MS spectra of compound 2h

MS spectra of compound 2i

MS spectra of compound 2j

MS spectra of compound 2k

MS spectra of compound 2l

MS spectra of compound 2n

MS spectra of compound 2o